

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
of Coastal Communities

Deliverable 6.6

Updated Data Management Plan Guide

1.0

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Executive Summary

This report is the first updated deliverable of Task 6.6 “Data Management plan” and updates first the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EmpowerUs project, funded by EU’s ‘EU Horizon Europe Programme’ on 1st October 2022 and will run for three years under the grant number 101059957.

The main objective of EmpowerUs DMP is to provide a comprehensive overview of all datasets gathered and generated as part of the project and to summarize the data management policy of the EmpowerUs consortium as it relates to these datasets. The methodology to produce the EmpowerUs DMP is based on the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) guidelines and follows the structure of Horizon Europe DMP template.

This updated version of the EmpowerUs DMP demonstrates the overall approach and policy for handling data management concerns on both an administrative and technological level. It reflects the status of the data that is collected, processed, or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. This includes for example topics like data and meta-data collection, publication, and deposition of open data. The EmpowerUs DMP adhere to the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

The current version summarises the current data collection activities that are happening for the project. It also discusses about the FAIR guidelines and data repository for data management. The DMP will evolve during the lifespan of the project. Next versions will refine and enhance policy aspects and will go into more detail regarding the datasets collected and produced by the EmpowerUs project partners.

Key words: Data Management Plan, EmpowerCoast, data accessibility, findability, interoperability

List of abbreviations

AL: Academic Lead

CA: Consortium Agreement

CO: Coordinator

DL: Deliverable Leader

DMP: Data Management Plan

FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets

GA: Grant Agreement

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

IAB: International Advisory Board

IB: Innovation Board

KER: Key Exploitable Results

MT: Management Team

OBPS: Observe ocean Best Practices Systems

OL: Ocean Literacy

REA: European Research Executive Agency

R&I: Research and Innovation

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

TCL: Transition Coastal Lab

TEP: Tailored Empowerment Program

WP: Work Package

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1. Introduction

Coastal regions are highly vulnerable to climate change as they are affected by multiple parameters such as rainfall, flooding, temperature, wind, wave height, sea-level-rise and erosion. The communities along these coasts face many challenges such as extreme weather events, land-subsidence, salt-water intrusion, decrease in fisheries resources due to climate change. Europe has a very long coastline as a centre for important economic, environmental, and social activities and sites. Important ports, offshore energy production, and fishing are all concentrated along the coast, and with consequently in recent years, marine-coastal conflicts have been growing consistently. EmpowerUs is a multidisciplinary project that will support coastal communities as they transition to becoming more environmentally, economically, and socially sustainable by recognizing these complex challenges and implementing integrated solutions.

The 3-year EmpowerUs project aims to support resilient, inclusive, and sustainable coastal development activities and empower coastal communities to start acting now. A co-design approach will be pursued along the 6 TCLs set up in the project to devise and demonstrate appropriate solutions. The assessment measures will involve the gathering, processing, and storage of a wide range of data sets pertaining to wide range of coastal climate parameters and adaptation assessment. The project will inspire and enable coastal communities to tackle the most pressing environmental, economic and social challenges that exist in their communities. Most of the research data will be managed, within the project life and beyond, through the EmpowerUs SharePoint platform, although permanent public repositories (Zenodo, but also Figshare, and Dryad) can be selected by project partners for facilitating the re-use of consolidated datasets.

In this context, the Data Management Plan (DMP), outlining the way that data are collected or generated within the project, how they will be organized, stored, and shared, is a critical element of the project. It specifies which data will be publicly available through public repositories and which will be available only to the consortium (confidential), as far as this is possible, from the project's initial stage. The DMP also provides motivations when versions or parts of the project research data cannot be openly shared; for EmpowerUs, it is expected that this can occur in relation to third-party copyright issues (in particular, for data collected at Coastal City levels), confidentiality, or personal data protection requirements.

This document is the update of DMP to be delivered at Month 24 (Deliverable D6.6). New versions DMPs should reflect changes such as those due to modifications with the emergence of new data standards, new releases of external datasets used by EmpowerUs, and, finally, the inclusion of new data sources and the documentation of new datasets produced by the project.

Section 2 (Data Summary) provides general information about the data usage in the project, namely the purpose and sources of data collection/generation in relation to the achievement of the project's goal. The description along with technical information about data formatting and size.

The Section 3 (Fair data) describes the general methodologies that the project will follow to ensure that data will be managed according to the FAIR principles¹ and recommended FAIR practices², with subsections specifically targeting the basic elements of FAIR principles. A specific section illustrates strategies to monitor the implementation of the FAIR approach by the EmpowerUs project. In this update, specific solutions for FAIR compliance

Section 4 (Allocation of resources) details how project resources are allocated to the management of research data. Following sections deal with the solutions adopted for Data security (Section 5), and for compliance with Ethical aspects (Section 6) crucial in EmpowerUs because significant project activities involve dealing with coastal communities and stakeholders. Finally, Section 7 provides a Summary of EmpowerUs research data. For each dataset that is released, relevant information will be provided highlighting specific methods adopted to be compliant with FAIR objectives.

1.2. Rationale

The EmpowerUs Data Management Plan (DMP) will collect data, develop algorithms and models to automatize data collection, enrichment, and analysis. The goal of the program is to foster access to data generated from the EmpowerUs project, so that the data becomes accessible, re-usable and benefit the various stakeholders. For the data gathering and storage, the consortium will ensure the secure environment, and that it will comply to the ethical and legal standards such as consent and/or anonymity of the data provider/owner for the use of data. The DMP will ensure that the General Data Protection Regulation³ (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679), which governs the management of data records including personal information, is followed.

1.3. Objectives

The EmpowerUs DMP will be accomplished through different dissemination and exploitation actions, to outline the policies and procedures to be followed by the consortium by ensuring that the data gathered and collected is managed correctly. These actions further aim at communicating project results to key stakeholders by engaging with the task leaders to organise workshops, educational activities and the publication of articles concerning projects results, to ensure open access policy for Horizon Europe project guidelines.

The DMP package will:

1. Cover the data management life cycle for the EmpowerUs project data collection, processing and/or generation.
2. Analyse the key components of the DMP that the consortium shall employ to manage all of the EmpowerUs data, documentation and metadata
3. Ensure that the research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR)
4. Create a list of data collected and generated, then preserve the data for long-term archival in accordance with the data policy requirements

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² *Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (Version 3.0, 26 July 2016)*, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

³ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

5. Ensure the ethical and legal compliance of the project.

The DMP will ensure effective external communication and dissemination of the EmpowerUs project results, including stakeholder engagement, to support uptake of knowledge results at different levels and maximise impact and legacy. It should serve as a manual for all data management procedures to be followed in the EmpowerUs project while also providing background information and rationale for each procedure in the context of Horizon Europe.

1.4. The DMP approach

EmpowerUs follows the EU horizon guidelines for open innovation. Open science is the key to allow knowledge to spread more quickly and make it easily accessible. Through the scientific publications and research data availability, the adaptations will progress more rapidly for the existing challenges. The approach is to follow the EU's Open Science Policy⁴ to acquire and generate data from multiple sources, saving and accessibility of that data. It is also expected that DMP will continue to do so after the project has ended using various available platforms. The DMP is a crucial component of the project in this context, as it details how the data has been gathered or generated within the project and how it will be organized, stored, and shared. Furthermore, since the beginning of the project, the DMP details which data is to be made available to the public through open repositories and which, to the extent practicable, is only to be made available to the consortium (confidential). Regarding data and information sensitivity, current law and policies are taken into consideration for various countries involved in the project.

All grants must manage the research data produced in projects supported by Horizon Europe. Each beneficiary is responsible for ensuring that the research data generated in the project is carefully managed in accordance with the FAIR principles ([AGA Article 17 – Annex 5](#)).

Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Partners are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the EmpowerUs project (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem.

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⁴https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

The data gathered and produced will have a metadata, however the form/format of the metadata has yet to be established. With the data gathered, a visual story map for blue justice stories will be created online and will be partially accessible to the public. As the project progresses, the accessibility also changes. Nevertheless, after the project completion, the publicly available data will remain online for five years. As part of the DMP, all EC reporting stages will be reviewed with regards to how the project responds to the FAIR principles.

1.5. DMP revision plan for EmpowerUs

EmpowerUs will acquire and generate data from multiple sources, and it is expected that it will continue to do so after the project has ended.

While the first version of the DMP primarily focused on data to be collected, the second version includes report on data produced in the framework of the project as well as non-sensitive data that can be made publicly accessible in open data repositories and registered at relevant catalogues. The final DMP report, which will include comprehensive information about the project's data collection and the data generated for all tasks, will be developed at the project's conclusion.

2. Data Summary

The project will require the collection, processing and storage of various datasets from all the EmpowerUs partners. As the data identification and collection activities are still ongoing,

As data identification and collection activities are ongoing, the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) primarily addressed the data summary with preliminary data collection techniques and approaches, with limited details on data format and storage requirements. The present (second) version included the summary report on project-generated data and non-sensitive data suitable for public access in open data repositories and relevant catalogues. While, the next (final) version of the data summary will be completed by the project's conclusion, providing comprehensive details on data collection and output for all tasks. A detailed descriptions of the datasets, accessibility and other questionnaire that are relevant to all the WPs for preparing the current DMP version are available in Annex 1.

An initial survey has been carried out from the EmpowerUs partners to gather the data information, each work-package (WP) and their data summary has been provided in the following sub-sections:

2.1. WP1: Project management and coordination

The data gathered in this work package will be in document format. The primary objective is to audit the entire project; however, there are no specific deliverables that may be provided in terms of data gathering or data production from this WP.

2.2. WP2: Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)

From WP2, **TCLs are one of the focal points for the EmpowerUs activities** as it will coordinate the design, implementation and evaluation activities.

The data will be stored in text format and potentially SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). The expected size of individual datasets ranges between a few MB and 1 GB. The data will preferentially be processed offline by individual experts, while the aggregated data, data necessary for functionality will be stored on designated project specific or institutional data (cloud) data store, such as SharePoint. Apart from local data that is subject to complex agreements, the data stored in these joint or institutional data stores will have full access policy for the project partners and will be considered for open access publication in open access repositories unless restricted by third-party copyrights or confidentiality agreements. The data gathered will be shared in accordance with EmpowerUs guidelines, which is mostly in publications and/or report formats.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of data sources used by WP2, licensing details will be provided in the next DMP, in case the secondary data is used by the TCLs.

Table 1- Summary of data sources used by WP 2

TCLs	Origin of the data	Data type	Data owner	Data format and the size (memory)
Bulgaria	Primary source (direct)	Interviews; surveys; Questionnaire	LMU	.doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx; and Approx 30mb
Cyprus	Primary source (direct)	Interviews; surveys; Questionnaire	CMMI	.doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx; and Approx 30mb
Finland	Primary source (direct)	Interviews; surveys; Questionnaire	LUKE	.doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx; and Approx 30mb
Ireland	Primary source (direct); Secondary source: Financial data from https://core.cro.ie/	Interviews; surveys; financial statements and balance sheets from companies	QUB	Primarily .doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx and .m4a files; and Approx 50 mb
Norway	Primary source (direct)	Interviews, Questionnaires, participant observation	NTI	.doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx and .m4a files; and Approx 150 mb
Spain	Primary source (direct)	Interviews; surveys; Questionnaire	UAB	.doc and .pdf format, some .xlsx and .m4a files; and Approx 50 mb

2.3. WP3: Participatory methods to support social transition and innovation

This work package will gather data through SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats), questionnaires and interviews. The data gathered until now is in the doc, xlsx, JPEG, PPT and pdf formats, and the size is 648MB while it may increase in coming months. Through the EmpowerUs SharePoint workspace, all partners have access to the data, however, part of the data will have limited access for the stakeholders from outside the EmpowerUs project to protect individuals and organizations, as per the Norwegian Centre for Research Data regulations. The expected outcomes accessible to the public will be in the form of report and peer-reviewed articles, pilot interventions including public events and activities.

2.4. WP4: Evidence-based, nature-based solutions for cross sectoral innovation

The main objective of this work package is to improve the ecological resilience by supporting the six TCLs in finding a range of nature-based solutions and social innovations. The tools to gather data for this WP are with problem tree, interviews, focus group, SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats), mental mapping, force field analysis, observation, questionnaire and any other means available to get the information such as co-creation tools. The data format is in doc, excel and/or pdf format with the current memory size of 1 MB that will be increased during the course of project. For the accessibility, the stakeholders will get their own folder with data (sensitive data are not openly accessible). Raw data from questionnaire surveys and interviews will be anonymized and partly restricted (and thus will be available for internal use only/within the project consortium). However, data will be published in the journals as open access and thus publicly available.

2.5. WP5: Synthesis of Inclusive Transition Mechanisms that enable just, sustainable outcomes.

The primary goal for this work package is to synthesise lessons and inputs from WP2, WP3 and WP4 by examining and identifying what social and cultural practices, economic activities and governance arrangements that are resilient under rapid change and uncertainty. By synthesising the challenges, barriers and preconditions across all TCLs, WP5 will produce a roadmap on the design of transition mechanisms and a handbook on inclusive methodologies that focus on equity. The results will be made available to the public as the project moves forward. To safeguard people and organizations, some of the qualitative data will be restricted, but the remaining data can still be obtained with the necessary authorization. As the type and extent of these datasets depend on work in progress, more details will be provided in the next version of the DMP.

Based on these sources and through WP activities, EmpowerUs is expected generate various forms of datasets. The partners (or the partner) that have contributed to each product will be considered as shared owners of the products. The different formats used are summarized in Table-2 Summary of data formats, facilitating re-use through deposit in permanent repositories.

Table 2-Summary of data formats

Type of data	Formats used during data processing and in SIP	Formats for sharing reuse and preservation
Numerical or \textual tabular data	Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx)	Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), Comma-separated values (.csv)
Qualitative textual data	Microsoft Word (.doc/.docx)	Microsoft Word (.doc/.docx) / Rich Text Format (.rtf) or text (.txt)
Audio data	mp3 format (.mp3)	Typically, they are destroyed after transcription
Video data	mpg format (.mp4)	Video are destroyed unless they are used to detect environmental features. These videos which will be utilized primarily for detecting environmental features will be preserved. In such cases, the video files will be retained for analysis purposes. However, the partners will ensure that any retention of video data complies with ethical guidelines and data protection regulations. Additionally, partner will consider implementing secure storage and access controls to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the data. Mpg will be used in this case
Vector data	ESRI shapefile, DBF, GeoJSON, KML	ESRI shapefile, DBF, GeoJSON, KML
Images	png, jpeg	png, jpeg

2.6. WP5: Synthesis of Inclusive Transition Mechanisms that enable just, sustainable outcomes.

The primary goal for this work package is to synthesise lessons and inputs from WP2, WP3 and WP4 by examining and identifying what social and cultural practices, economic activities and governance arrangements that are resilient under rapid change and uncertainty. By synthesising the challenges, barriers and preconditions across all TCLs, WP5 will produce a roadmap on the design of transition mechanisms and a handbook on inclusive methodologies that focus on equity. The results will be made available to the public as the project moves forward. To safeguard people and organizations, some of the qualitative data will be restricted, but the remaining data can still be obtained with the necessary authorization. As the type and extent of these datasets depend on work in progress, more details will be provided in the next version of the DMP.

2.7. WP6: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Ocean Literacy.

WP6 will implement the PDEC with the involvement of all partners and outline concrete and targeted measures related to communication, dissemination, knowledge management, and exploitation activities for EmpowerUs and deliver tailored knowledge transfer plans for Key Exploitable Results 12 (KERs). It will further involve the TEPs conducted by TCLs in (WP2) and ensure to reach end-users with the support of WP leaders and the Innovation partners. As per the requirement of EC, access policy to

scientific publications will be implemented. All the publication, in addition to the publisher's archive, will be also stored in an online repository, where it can be easily linked to deposited datasets and at partners' institutional repositories. For project internal administrative needs as well as external dissemination, community development, and exploitation operations, WP6 data is primarily engaged in user account and profile information. This includes both personal data of EmpowerUs partners staff used to manage the project's mailing lists and document repository and personal data of outside users used to provide functionality to the EmpowerUs community (newsletters, event invitations, etc.). The datasets include details like names, organizations, email addresses, roles, etc. that are mostly gathered directly from the users when they register on the relevant websites and confirmed. The first version of the DMP is submitted in M6 of the project in a document format (March 2023), while the second one is submitted in M18 (March 2024). As the project progresses, the data will be made available in EmpowerUs website in the forms of images, videos, and documents. There will be revisions to the DMP and will be made during the project as visibility increases around the nature, volume, formats, etc. of the data. The final DMP should be reviewed and updated, at the end of the project (M36).

2.8. WP7: Ethics requirement

The consortium of this project places a high priority on data protection and ethical research practices. When conducting research, good ethics follow all procedures to guard against the misuse of sensitive data. For this project, the consortium seeks to guarantee this. WP7 ensures that the partners must comply with the ethics and research integrity (see GA Article 34 from Horizon Europe grants manual webpage mentioned in the annex 3 links). The data collected will be kept in document form for the benefit of the stakeholders, and it will adhere strictly to the EU project ethics guidelines. Further, the document outlines will be regularly updated in the EmpowerUs website.

3. FAIR data

This document considers the latest Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe. The EmpowerUs project partners should make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) and ensure that is soundly managed, allowing for maximum knowledge circulation. This DMP describes the data management procedures that are followed according to the FAIR principles and the Horizon Europe guidelines for their implementation. To prepare the DMP FAIR data, we used Horizon Europe grants manual data management plan template. The template is a set of questions that one should answer with a level of detail appropriate to the project, however the detail of the project is ongoing and will be revised in the next versions of the DMP. EmpowerUs will ensure all its data are findable by depositing all project-generated data underlying EmpowerUs produced, peer-reviewed publications in open access online repositories.

Identifiers

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are important because they unambiguously identify data and facilitate data citation. EmpowerUs partners will select data repositories that assign a persistent identifier e.g., a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Partners will also be encouraged to register with ORCID to create a personal professional ID.

Naming conventions

File names will include version numbers, and time-frame in terms of month. Typically, the name convention will follow with WP (Work package number), or the task number (e.g. T2.1) or deliverable (e.g. D2.2).

The naming convention for each work package is described as follows:

WPNumber_TaskNumber_PartnerName_DatasetName_Version_DateOfStorage .

Search keywords to optimize possibilities for re-use

Identifiers: All open EmpowerUs results deposited in a repository will provide search keywords together with their metadata, further clarity is provided in 3.1.5. Keywords for open data will be selected from controlled vocabularies that are suitable for the specific type of the data (see 3.3.3).

Metadata and repositories

Metadata is data that provides information about data. The main metadata categories for EmpowerUs research data are descriptive (title, abstract, author, and keywords, technical characteristics), structural (pages, chapters, tables, pictograms, diagrams) and administrative (file type, permissions, and when and how the file was created). Metadata is as important as the data itself as it allows applications to categorise and archive datasets, facilitating users to easily search and find relevant datasets.

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find through online search. To ensure the automatic discoverability of datasets and services, machine-readable metadata are essential. EmpowerUs has its own publicly available website, that gives complete details about the publication, its progress and the partners associated. The partners will be asked to select the most appropriate data repositories that facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are the basic principles for the Horizon Europe project to comply with. Although during the project life, data will be managed through the common Sharepoint and regularly updating EmpowerUs webpage, for the publication of project results, each research teams will deposit and describe the relative underlying dataset(s), keywords and unique identifiers to find them. Further, the data can be accessible through their Institutional **repositories** with a unique persistent identifier, such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

OpenAIRE is a platform funded and supported by European Commission with the mission to shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research. Each dataset owner will ensure that their chosen repositories disseminate (meta)data to OpenAIRE to maximise data sharing, finding and re-use of research outputs from EmpowerUs. Any repository that is listed in this DMP is interoperable with OpenAIRE; partners who wish to use a different repository may inquire to the Coordinating Team (NRI team) to check whether it disseminates to OpenAIRE. If it does not, the Coordinating Team may contact OpenAIRE to see whether it can be added.

Although during the project life data will be managed through the SharePoint, at the publication of project results each research teams will deposit and describe the relative underlying dataset(s) (see Table 3 - Example of dataset description form for EmpowerUs publication) in the identified public data repositories, but also their Institutional repositories, if existing, provided that they can attribute

persistent unique identifiers to the deposited items. As mentioned, EmpowerUs partners/academic lead (AL) will be asked to select the most appropriate data repositories that facilitate the findings, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are basic principles with which Horizon Europe projects must comply. Some of the repositories suggested are mentioned in Annex 3.

EmpowerUs partners are also suggested to consider the Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) and Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) for useful listings of repositories that might be suitable for WP outputs.

Table 3 - Example of dataset description form for EmpowerUs publication

Status:	WPX:: Task X.1: (short title of the dataset)
ID# Number	
Type of PID (Repository)	
PID (publisher version of record)	
Type of publication	
Link to publication	
Title of the scientific publication	
Authors	
Title of the Journal or equivalent	
Number of the journal, proceeding or book	
ISSN or eISSN	
Publisher	
Month of publication	
Year of publication	
Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication?	
Peer-reviewed	
Book title	
Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	
Type of publishing venue	
Article processing costs	
Project Partner(s) involved	
Contact details main partner involved	

3.2. Making data Accessible

To encourage **re-use and further application** of project results, all EmpowerUs **data** underlying peer-reviewed scientific publications will be made available via open access platforms for verification and re-use, unless the data-owner can justify why data cannot be made openly accessible. To achieve this, the datasets deposited will have all relevant documentation and explanation, and all files will be converted to standard, well-documented open formats. However, should there be a data type required to be closed to maintain privacy/confidentiality, the Coordinating Team will assess the justifications and make the final decision, based on the [permitted exceptions for underlying data](#)⁵. The assessment includes the following elements when considering confidentiality of datasets:

⁵ Exceptions to open access to research data underlying publications in the Open Research Europe are permitted according to the relevant policy of Horizon Europe. These consider the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security

- When collected data is from third party and it denies the accessibility through EmpowerUs for confidentiality issues.
 - Protection of personal information or the stakeholder who provided the data for sensitivity and safety.
 - Legal issues relating to data used.
 - Any other legitimate reasons.
- To allow data sharing as much as possible, legitimate actions will be adopted such as:
- When collected data, copyrights will be obtained from third party owners, wherever is applicable.
 - Acknowledge the re-used data for external users and also for internal purposes is from third party and it denies the accessibility through EmpowerUs for confidentiality issues, by providing all relevant documentation and explanation for the data and the datasets, including the procedures adopted to obtain them, versioning, and software for reading data in case of non-standardize formats.
 - Obtain the consent from citizens and stakeholders carried out by WP3, WP4 and WP6 surveys and interviews
 - In case of copyright on raw data derived, collected or elaborated from pre-existing databases or from other original sources (i.e., papers, journal articles, book chapters, reports, video and audio sources), collected data will be made available if the reproduction and sharing are allowed by expressed permission of the right holders or by applicable copyright exceptions and exemptions.

Wherever necessary, the EmpowerUs DMP indicates the versions or parts of the datasets that cannot be freely shared providing the specific motivations. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement (CA) and are in line with the reasons for opting out.

Repository: EmpowerUs will have results repositories that will be openly accessible in accordance with Horizon Europe guideline policy for open access to research data. Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (primarily published in academic journals), research data are other ways of providing accessibility. For disseminating open access papers, including academic social network sites such as ResearchGate or Academia etc, are possible, for which, an electronic copy of the publication has to be deposited in suitable open access repository. However, the Horizon Europe project guidelines also encourage to use of other online repositories that are mentioned in the above sections. To automate the process of reporting scientific publications and other research data, there are different ways such as green open access and gold open access that can be used depending upon the time frame under which the data needs to be disseminated. The EmpowerUs partners are encouraged to use such actions as per their needs.

Software for accessibility: The EmpowerUs partners may not use any code to access data, the basic software tools usable are listed in Table 4. Considering formats listed in Table 1 - Summary of data formats, there will be no need to use specifically tailored software to access project dataset, since prior to the deposit researchers will convert the data into open formats. In case agreements with third parties will restrict the access to specific users, the access will be managed through the permission system allowed by the cloud service and the identity of the accessing person will be ascertained before data provision.

Table 4: Software/tools used for DMP data accessibility.

Tools/Software

obligations, the obligation to protect personal data and other legitimate constraints. Where open access is not provided to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results, authors should provide the relevant access needed to validate the conclusions to the extent their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (see [Add a Data Availability Statement to Your Article](#)).

open spreadsheet and document editors, such as <i>OpenOffice</i> or <i>LibreOffice</i>
free CSV file viewers, such as <i>CSV viewer</i>
open or free image viewers
VLC for mp3 and mpg

3.3. Making data Interoperable

Interoperable data allows exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins).

Project partners should consider from the outset identifying the most suitable file types and structures they can utilise to support external interoperability once published. Specifically, this includes what tools will be needed to validate the results, e.g. specialised qualitative/quantitative analysis tools and analysis protocols. Where possible, partners should provide these instruments themselves alongside the open access dataset.

Partners must select repositories which observe Ocean Best Practices Systems and OpenAIRE guidelines for interoperability, including OBPS standards for data and metadata generation, storage, labelling and transfer and OpenAIRE guidelines for data archives. These guidelines can be found online (<https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/> and <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>).

3.4. Making data Re-Usable

A Creative Commons license, ideally Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY-4.0⁶) is advised for owners of open results produced from the EmpowerUs project notwithstanding the restrictions. The authors can preserve the ownership of their work through scientific publications, and open access repositories can allow accessibility to a wide range of stakeholders as well as to the public.

In order to preserve ownership of their work's copyright and deposit the publication in an Open Access repository, authors of scientific papers resulting from the EmpowerUs project are advised to negotiate a deal with the article's scientific publisher. The research data required to verify the findings of the scientific articles will be given open access simultaneously with the publication.

After the project is completed, third parties can still use any open results that were produced by the project and stored in the appropriate repository. If open access to specific research data is required to verify a scientific publication is prohibited by confidentiality, security and privacy obligations, the data may be deposited in a restricted repository and access may be granted upon request and under the terms of a restricted license. The open results that are deposited in a repository will be available up to 5 years after the completion the project.

The data quality assurance and process will be described by the ethics section (See Section 6). This will progress, from the first results published/produced for the EmpowerUs project.

⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode.en>

3.5. Enforcing FAIR approach in EmpowerUs

The previous sections have described the general concepts of FAIR approaches and the technical solutions to enforce EmpowerUs management in the project. However, since creation of datasets, and data formats chosen as well for generated data, some guidance and supervision are needed.

In particular, support and training provided by WP6 (Task 6.3 lead by ATU) to partners and TCLs about open repository usage. For this purpose, the continuous reporting log has been proposed and approved by the EmpowerUs consortium, which is available in EmpowerUs SharePoint to all the partners, with guidelines:

- All EmpowerUs partners are contractually obligated to provide the EC with a continuous log of their publications, dissemination, and communication activities. This information must be added to the Continuous Reporting area of the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal (SEDIA), and reported on in the Periodic Report to the EC.
- Prior notice for deposited datasets and publications is required.
- Notify publication dataset to EmpowerUs partners via email to partner through email.

The reporting document includes three worksheets: 1. Publications; 2. Dissemination Activities; 3. Communication Activities. The procedure applies when a dataset is proposed by a partner for uploading to a permanent repository and consists of the following steps:

Please use the following instructions to help. An example is provided (in yellow) on each worksheet.

Continuous Reporting of **Publications**:

The following information is required for **every publication** and is part of mandatory EC reporting:

- **Type of PID (repository):** DOI, Handle, ARK, URL, pURL, Other, None.
- **Types of publications:** Article in Journal; Publication in conference proceedings/workshop; Book/Monograph; Chapter in a Book; Thesis/Dissertation; Other.
- **Title of the scientific publication**
- **Authors of the publication**
- **Name of publisher**
- **Open Access:** Hybrid (Accessible via open license in a subscription journal), full open access (OA journal, no restrictions) or full subscription (No Guarantees, no reuse rights)
- **Is it a peer-reviewed publication?**

Note: Once research has been published, please inform ERINN (contact: donnchadh@erinn.eu), so that the publication can be added to the project website.

Task leaders will examine the dataset for compliance with DMP regulations, especially regarding naming and the dataset description. If the dataset includes data derived from questionnaires or other potentially ethically sensitive data, explicit compliance must be stated, and consent from WP7 must be obtained before collecting the data/information. Furthermore, a list of datasets and their characteristics will be maintained in the DMP.

4. Allocation of resources

Building on existing open science resources and Horizon Europe guidelines, the DMP will document the policies and procedures to be followed by the EmpowerUs consortium for managing all data generated and collected during and after the project, including scientific outputs, new methodologies, protocols, processes, new approaches, modelling and digital database (EmpowerCoast).

The costs related to open access to research data will be covered through the Horizon Europe grant which is in compliance with the Grant Agreement. EmpowerUs has allocated a part of overall WP6 budget for these activities. For the open access research data, the Horizon Europe grant guidelines will be strictly followed. At present, the EmpowerUs project grant includes, €24,000 for the cloud-based knowledge sharing platforms, €20,000 for the WP2 data management system, €2,000 for the conferences, and €3,000 for open access publications.

Data management activities concern the whole project and needs to be coordinated and monitored both at project and work package level. Data management is also linked to publication of project results and thus dissemination activities. The primary responsibility is held by ATU and ERINN Innovation, while all the project partners will contribute through the activity updates. DMP versions will be prepared by ATU through surveys.

The long-term preservation of data as per the Horizon Europe guidelines will be available up to 5 years after the completion the project in the data repository. The Zenodo repository is encouraged to use by all the partners. The EmpowerUs consortium will decide, how and how long the data will be retained.

5. Data security

During the duration of the project, relevant research data has been managed through SharePoint. At each partner institution, research data will be stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives accessible through institutional passwords periodically modified according to national law provisions for data security and protected by regularly updated antiviruses. None of the project data will be left inadvertently available. All the research materials stored in computers are subject to regular backup to safeguard them from accidental losses. The data results are encouraged to put in Zenodo as well for long term preservation.

The selected data repositories, which have specified preservation standards, enable long-term preservation of public data. For instance, few of the partners like QUB started using Zenodo repository and they will be kept for the duration of the repository, and best efforts will be made to integrate all information into appropriate substitute institutional and/or subject-based repositories in the event of closure.

Best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories. Handling of sensitive data is described Section 6.

6. Ethical aspects

All currently identified ethical parameters to be obeyed are documented in WP7 - Ethics requirements. Before making the data accessible, all relevant open access datasets will also address ethical issues. The EmpowerUs project will not produce research results which are sensitive to personal and ethical concerns. The EmpowerUs project has assigned an ethics and security board, which will monitor and make decisions related to the ethics and security. Additional details will be reported, as needed, in future versions of the DMP.

Further on, it is communicated by WP7, where informed consent is needed and how to get them, e.g., addressing informed consent procedure for communication with stakeholders. Additional details are provided in WP7 Ethics requirements reports/manuals, whereas consent forms are work in progress at present. As of now, two workshops have been conducted in each TCL. NRI is currently working on the updated deliverable for WP7, that also include developing consent forms for the stakeholders.

The EmpowerUs project involves human participants through particularly in WP2 TCL pilot studies and WP5. As part of the recruitment process and when working with participants, the EmpowerUs project follows key principles regarding respect, participation, consent, and anonymity for the best interests of all voluntary participants drafted by WP5 partners.

All personal data collected within the EmpowerUs project from questionnaires, interviewers, surveys and focus groups are carefully protected in compliance with relevant national data protection legislation of the EU member states implementing the European Directive 95/46/EC and with the procedures defined by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

International Codes of Ethics such as those developed by ESOMAR⁷ (International Code on Market, Opinion and Social Research Data Analytics) will be adhered to. A Consent Form for some activities will be requested to participants except in the instance that the research constitutes a minimal risk to participants (see AAPOR definition of minimal risk research).

All the participants recruited will receive an Information Sheet translated into their local language before being invited to sign on as participant citizen scientists. The sign-on document is called Written Consent form. This will ensure understanding of contributions, responsibilities, outputs, transfer of knowledge production and lessons learned once the initial framework and methodology have been designed and implemented.

These information sheets will include:

- A brief outline of the aims of the research and its intended purposes
- The duration and extent of involvement
- Information on their rights and the nature of informed consent. In particular, the right to withdraw from the research at any time, even after they have been recruited as a participant,
- A guarantee for confidentiality and anonymity and an explanation of how data will be processed and stored
- Information sheets shall be adapted to different TCLs background and language, if necessary
- Contact details of TCL leaders, where study participants could request further information
- Explanation on who is funding the research and for what purpose
- Explanation on who will have access to any data that participants provide

⁷ <https://standards.esomar.org/resources/international-codes>

- Brief explanation on where research findings will be published
- Clarification of possible uses to which data may be put in future.
- An acknowledgement that they understand their rights

Written consent form shall be signed by parents/guardians if willing minors become involved in the research. In the instance of engaging minors, informed consent form should contain all the relevant information for a child to understand the meaning of consent and that participation is voluntary can be withdrawn at any stage.

All information will include notes on anonymity, recording, data use, voluntary participation, the possibility of withdrawal, availability of research results and principal research contacts. For the different groups (adults/minors) confidentiality and anonymity will be always guaranteed, unless the written agreement with the respondent is different.

8. Conclusion

The EmpowerUs Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the policies and procedures to be followed by the EmpowerUs consortium for managing the data generated and collected during and after the project. It should serve as a manual for all data management procedures to be followed in the project while also providing background information and rationale for each procedure in the context of Horizon Europe.

It is a living document that will be continually updated throughout the lifetime of the project. While there are formal reviews planned for the document (D6.2 (in M6), D6.6 (in M18), and D6.7 (in M36)), the DMP will be updated at regular intervals and following the end of official project reporting periods. The next steps for this document includes all the semantics, further methodology elaboration, participant and stakeholder involvement, and the identification of areas that require special attention. The next DMP update will be the final update in M36 (D6.7).

Annex 1: Daya Survey template for version 2

The EmpowerUs data Survey Template is used to collect information on used and produced datasets according to the requirements of the EmpowerUs Data Management Plan with help of EmpowerUs's technical coordination site ([https:// EmpowerUs-project.eu/](https://EmpowerUs-project.eu/)).

1	Email
2	Name
3	Name of Partner organisation
4	Work package number
5	TCL name (If the partner is from TCL or leave it blank)
6	Location
7	Email address
8	What pilot programmes are you considering for the study area ? (Please answer if it is relevant to you)
9	Please describe your data type. Example: Surveys and interviews, historical natural extreme events like hurricanes, storms, inundation etc; socio-economic data like population, income, tourism dev...
10	What tools did you use (are you using) to collect the data (You can select multiple choices)
11	If "Others" in the survey, mention the tool
12	What is the format and the size (memory) of the data delivered until now? (Example: doc/ASCII/JPEG format, 2 MB) Note: Please look into you folder for collected data
13	What is the origin of the data that you are using for the EmpowerUs project? The data can be primary or secondary (available), if it is secondary, please provide the source details: Web link, lic...
14	Will the data you've gathered/generated be useful for other stakeholders in the future? If so, will it be made accessible to them?
15	With which stakeholders have you collaborated until now to achieve your working objectives? Please specify the type and the name of the organizations, (mention the guessed/thoughtful one, you wa...
16	What is the discoverability of the data your work package generates (i.e. the metadata)? What form or format will the metadata describing your data take? For example, how much of the generated dat...
17	How do you ensure that your data is findable? (Please select one or more options)
18	Will your data be openly available? If any part of data is restricted, please provide a justification explaining why ? If your data is (partly-) restricted, is there any access code required to ge...
19	Can a third-party use/re-use your generated data ?
20	Does your output need any specific tools or software to access it?
21	If yes for the above survey, can it be re-used even after the end of the project? (Specify the length of time that data can be reused).
22	If "No" for the above survey, explain why (need to give rationale, as per FAIR guidelines)
23	Does your data require a license to be re-used and re-distributed widely? (As per FAIR policy, data is encouraged to be available to wider communities/stakeholders)
24	Does your data have back-up/ data-recovery facility?

25	What data-recovery facility are you using for the data at present ?
26	Is your data safely stored in any certified storage repositories for long-term preservation and curation?
27	Does your gathered data have any ethical or legal considerations that can have an impact on data sharing? For example: 1. The organizations with ownership of data and should be acknowledged; 2. ...
28	Do project stakeholders/partners involved in the EmpowerUs project have access to the processes and results? Do they require permission from you to re-use them? (This query aims to comprehend the ...
29	If "Other" (elaborate, example: permission needed from the owner or simply an acknowledgment/reference needed to re-use the data))
30	Are these same processes/outcomes available to public?
31	If "No" for the above survey, what part of the outcome will be accessible to the public?
32	Which style of documentary (activities) can be expected as output from your task? (Example: campaigning, strategic, operational, regulatory, legislative and so on)

Annex 2 – Online Open-Access Resources & Useful Links

Open Science in Horizon Europe

- Open Science: <https://openscience.eu>
- Open Research Europe: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

FAIR Findable (repositories)

- Directory of Open-Access Repositories: <http://www.opendoar.org/>
- Registry of Research Data Repositories: <https://www.re3data.org/>
- ZENODO Open-Access Data Repository: <https://zenodo.org/>
- INSPIRE: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>
- EMODNET: <https://emodnet.eu/en>
- Copernicus: <https://www.copernicus.eu/en/library>
- Horizon Results Platform (HRP) [Horizon Results Platform \(europa.eu\)](https://horizonresultsplatform.europa.eu/)
- The official portal for European data: <https://data.europa.eu/en>
- European Open science Cloud: <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

FAIR: Findable (Identifiers)

- Making Data 'Findable' using Persistent Identifiers: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>
- Using Identifiers for Open Access- for Authors and Research Materials: http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/dae/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=4607

FAIR: Findable (Metadata)

- Oceanographic specific vocabularies for metadata: <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/vocabularies/>
- Explanations of Scientific Metadata: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-reference-manual/chapters-production/scientific-metadata>
- Metadata Standards Directory Working Group: <http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>
- Open Data and Metadata Standards: https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/2015-05/d2.1.2_training_module_2.2_open_data_quality_v1.00_en.pdf
- Use of DataCite for metadata provisions: https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/use_of_datacite.html

FAIR: Interoperable

- OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, Data Archives, and CRIS Managers based on CERIF-XML: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

FAIR: Reusable (licensing)

- Creative Commons licensing : <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>
- Advice on commercialisation of research data: <https://eudat.eu/data-access-and-re-use>
- Licensing Wizard: <https://b2share.eudat.eu/>
- IPR Helpdesk Advice on seeking IP Professionals: <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Guide-IP-professionals.pdf>
- IPR Helpdesk Factsheet on IPR Valuation: <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/Fact-Sheet-IP-Valuation.pdf>

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